

Synthesis and mesomorphic properties of 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one

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Abstract : Synthesis of 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one and the structure was confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, Mass spectral data, their liquid crystalline properties were determined by polarizing optical microscopy, differential scanning calorimetry. These 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one derivatives were found to exhibit mesomorphism over a wide temperature range.

Keywords : Liquid crystal (LC), mesophase, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), polarizing microscope (PM).

Introduction

Naturally occurring oxygen hetero cyclic compounds, flavonoids¹ are isoflavonoids exhibit aromatic character and may possess quasi planarity due to conjugation in the molecule. Like many natural products containing heterocycles in their structures, such as flavones and coumarin derivatives, isoflavone compounds in biological systems can show liquid crystalline behaviour^{2,3}. Isoflavone derivatives constitute the largest number of compounds among the natural isoflavonoids. The mesogenicity of several isoflavone derivatives has been reported previously³⁻¹¹. It has been well documented that the study of liquid crystalline compounds is very important for the continual development and understanding of the field of molecular engineering. In our research, we focused on modifying existing molecules, particularly natural products, has shown to be a viable approach leading to new compounds showing liquid crystalline properties. Here we report the results and investigation details.

Experimental

Synthesis : A mixture of resorsinol (**1**) (3 mmol), *p*-hydroxy phenyl acetic acid (**2**) (3 mmol) and BF₃.Et₂O

(1.94 ml, 15.3 mmol) was heated (85 °C) for 90 min with stirring resulting the formation of 2,4,4'-trihydroxy deoxybenzoin (**3**). The mixture was then cooled to 10 °C and DMF (4.6 ml) was added dropwise. In another flask, DMF (8 ml) was cooled to 10 °C and PCl₅ (0.939 g, 4.5 mmol) was added in small portions. The mixture was then allowed to stand at 55 °C for 20 min. The pale pink colored solution containing *N,N*-dimethyl (chloromethylene) ammonium chloride was then added to the above reaction mixture slowly. During the addition, the temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained below 27 °C. The mixture was then stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction mixture was added slowly into HCl (0.1 *N*). 7-Hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (**4**) precipitated, filtered off, washed with water and air dried. 7-Hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (**4**) which separated out as a sticky mass were extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with water, brine and dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed under vacuum using a rotary evaporator and 7-hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (**4**) was obtained and further purified by column chromatography on silica, using ethyl acetate : hexane as elute.

Scheme 1

7-Hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (4) :

IR (ν_{max} , KBr) : 3423, 3199, 1632, 1610, 1594, 1523, 1462, 1386, 1243, 1194, 1096, 882, 843, 767; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO/TMS, 400 MHz) : 9.9 (1H, s), 8.3 (1H, s), 7.83 (1H, s), 7.81–7.82 (1H, d), 7.66–7.69 (2H, d), 7.12–7.14 (1H, d), 6.625–6.702 (1H, m), 6.612–6.617 (2H, d); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (DMSO/TMS, 100 MHz) : 175.3, 162.0, 157.3, 156.6, 151.3, 129.4, 126.9, 123.9, 122.3, 116.6, 114.8, 114.6, 113.7, 101.8; Mass ion (m/e) : 255 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

Compound (4) on reaction with long chain fatty acid chloride (RCOCl, R = undecyl, lauryl, stearyl, palmityl) in DMAP and dichloromethane at reflux temperature yielded 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (5) derivatives (6–9). The synthetic route is shown in Scheme 1. All the esters were purified by column chromatography with *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent. These products were recrystallized from methanol and purity of these above esters was checked by TLC and HPLC (97–99%).

Synthesis of 7-palmitoyloxy-3-(4-palmitoyloxyphenyl)-

4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (8) : 7-Hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (4) and palmitoyl chloride (prepared by action of SOCl_2 in palmitic acid and palmitoyl chloride thus prepared was distilled at reduced pressure) were refluxed in the presence of DMAP in DCM for 5–6 h. After usual workup, it yields a crude ester. Purification of the crude ester over a column of silica gel eluting with *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) afforded 7-palmitoyloxy-3-(4-palmitoyloxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (8). Purity of this compound was checked by TLC and HPLC. The structure of compound (8) was confirmed by IR, $^1\text{H NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ and Mass spectral data.

7-Palmitoyloxy-3-(4-palmitoyloxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (8) :

IR (ν_{max} KBr) : 3051, 2920, 2854, 1759, 1709, 1643, 1457, 1419, 1265, 1052, 1024, 821; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO + CDCl_3/TMS , 400 MHz) : 0.84–0.89 (6H, s), 1.25 (72H, brs), 1.57–1.58 (6H, m), 2.23–2.36 (6H, d), 6.84–6.87 (2H, d), 6.89–6.93 (1H, m), 7.34–7.35 (1H, d), 7.36–7.37 (1H, d), 7.91 (1H, s), 8.03–8.06 (2H, d); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (DMSO + CDCl_3/TMS , 100 MHz) : 174.8, 173.1, 163.3, 158, 156.7, 150.8, 129.1, 129.0, 126.5, 120, 114.4,

114.2, 101.5, 33.2, 30.8, 29.6, 28.4, 28.1, 23.9, 21.6, 13.2; Mass ion (*m/e*) : 731 (M^+).

7-Undecyloxy-3-(4-undecyloxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (6) :

IR (ν_{\max} , KBr) cm^{-1} : 2954, 2918, 2851, 1743, 1707, 1640, 1515, 1469, 1361, 1231, 1179, 1133, 920, 832, 786, 719; ^1H NMR (DMSO + CDCl_3/TMS , 400 MHz) : 0.86–0.88 (6H, s), 1.26 (28H, brs), 1.52–1.57 (4H, m), 2.21–2.32 (4H, t), 6.85–6.89 (2H, d), 7.13–7.21 (1H, m), 7.31–7.39 (2H, d), 7.51–7.61 (1H, d), 8.10 (1H, d), 8.22 (1H, d); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO+ CDCl_3/TMS , 100 MHz) : 174.5, 171.6, 158.5, 155, 153.5, 152.9, 128.8, 126.1, 120.4, 118.3, 114.2, 109.2, 33.0, 32.95, 30.5, 28.2, 27.9, 27.8, 27.6, 23.7, 23.4, 21.3, 12.9.

7-Lauroyloxy-3-(4-lauroyloxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (7) :

IR (ν_{\max} , KBr) cm^{-1} : 2956, 2909, 2843, 1742, 1698, 1682, 1627, 1599, 1523, 1512, 1473, 1249, 1090, 947, 843, 728, 690; ^1H NMR (DMSO+ CDCl_3/TMS , 400 MHz) : 0.85–0.88 (6H, s), 1.26 (32H, m), 1.51–1.56 (4H, s), 2.32–2.35 (4H, m), 6.81–6.85 (2H, d), 6.87–6.89 (1H, m), 7.34–7.36 (1H, d), 7.38–7.41 (1H, d), 7.88–7.95 (1H, s), 8.10–8.15 (2H, d); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO+ CDCl_3/TMS , 100 MHz) : 176.1, 172.9, 161.3, 159.2, 155.7, 150.9, 129.2, 129.1, 125.9, 120.2, 114.5, 114.3, 101.3, 34.0, 31.6, 29.3, 29.0, 28.9, 24.7, 22.4, 13.9.

7-Stearoyloxy-3-(4-stearoyloxyphenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (9) :

IR (ν_{\max} , KBr) cm^{-1} : 2954, 2918, 2818, 1759, 1702, 1603, 1547, 1505, 1420, 1200, 1164, 926, 838, 724; ^1H NMR (DMSO+ CDCl_3/TMS , 400 MHz) : 0.86–0.89 (6H, s), 1.25 (56H, brs), 1.617–1.635 (4H, m), 2.22–2.25

(4H, t), 6.84–6.87 (2H, d), 6.88–6.96 (2H, m), 7.11–7.18 (1H, d), 7.45–7.57 (1H, d), 7.94 (1H, d), 8.03–8.18 (1H, d); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO+ CDCl_3/TMS , 100 MHz) : 174, 172, 163, 156.1, 155, 151.7, 129.4, 126.3, 122.7, 121.7, 116.8, 114.4, 114.2, 101.4, 33.2, 28.5, 28.4, 28.2, 28.1, 28.0, 23.9, 21.6, 13.9.

Differential scanning calorimeter study :

Compound (**8**) 10 mg, dried completely was placed in a aluminium sample pane and sealed. The compound was studied for differential scanning calorimetric data at a heating rate 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The phase transition temperatures and the enthalpy (ΔH) were recorded. The 7-palmitoyloxy-3-(4-palmitoyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one exhibited two mesophases, first mesophase was in between the temperature 43.79–55.1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, enthalpy (ΔH) is 59.28 J/g, and the second mesophase was in between the temperature 59.1–75.7 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, enthalpy (ΔH) is 0.677 J/g, see Fig. 1 details. In order to further confirm the mesophase, compound (**8**) was studied using polarizing microscope at rate of 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The observed texture was recorded and presented in Fig. 2. Similarly compounds (**6**, **7**, **9**) were studied for differential scanning calorimetric data at a heating rate 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The phase transition temperature and the enthalpy (ΔH) were recorded, presented in Table 1.

Results and discussion

We examined that liquid crystal properties of 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one which are not reported earlier by any research group. Hence we synthesized 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one esters (Scheme 1) and their structure was confirmed by IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and its mass spectral data. The newly synthesized compounds were examined for

Table 1. DSC Thermographic data of 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones derivatives (**6-8**) (DSC Q2000 V24.9 Build 121)

Compd.	Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ crystal (K)- mesophase (S_1)	Enthalpy (ΔH) K- S_1 mj/mg	Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ S_1 -Isotropic	Enthalpy (ΔH) S_1 -Imj/mg
6	37.12–48.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	14.88 J/g	74.95–101.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	112.6 J/g
7	42.0–52.75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	21.03 J/g	59.8–65.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	0.21 J/g
8	43.79–59.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	59.28 J/g	59.1–75.75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 61.31–73.75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	0.67 J/g 140.8 J/g

Fig. 1. DSC diagram of compound (8).

Fig. 2. Schilern texture observed on cooling isotropic liquid to mesophase region of compound (8).

liquid crystal properties. During the course of our studies on thermotropic liquid crystals of hetero aromatic compounds, it is observed that 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones derivatives (6-9) displays mesophase on wide range of temperature.

Observation of data from Table 1 viz. the mesophase region and the heat of transition (ΔH), it is very clear that these esters exhibit mesophase from or above 37–102 °C. All newly synthesised compounds (6-8), except compound (9) exhibited two mesophases. It is interesting to note that the phase transition temperature and enthalpy (ΔH) values are increasing with increasing paraffinic chain length. Compound (6) (7-undecyloxy-3-(4-undecyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones) exhibited mesophase in between the temperature 37.12–48.3 °C, enthalpy (ΔH) is 14.88 J/g, but 7-stearoyloxy-3-(4-stearoyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one exhibited mesophase was in between the temperature 61.3–73.75 °C, enthalpy (ΔH) is 140.8 J/g. It is interesting to note that all the synthesized new 7-acyloxy-3-(4-acyloxyphenyl)-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one esters (6-9) exhibited first mesophase at lower temperature. All the compounds are potential for further study to explore room temperature liquid crystals, which are aimed

for industrial applications.

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